

ENHANCING DIGITAL PRESERVATION STRATEGIES: NAVIGATING THE EOSC EDEN PROJECT

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Abstract - The introduction of FAIR, CARE and TRUST principles to the research data management domain in general and the importance of digital preservation processes to keep deposited digital research objects FAIR over time, has a substantial impact on digital archives managing these diverse and growing volumes of content. Limited availability of resources (energy, capacity) and high maintenance requirements (diversity of formats and community needs) leads to archives being confronted with deciding which data to preserve. Whereas libraries and archives typically have overarching collection policies and guidelines for analogue and digital materials, digital research data repositories often find themselves starting from scratch. The EU-funded EOSC EDEN (2025 - 2027) project aims to address the issues by standardizing digital preservation and data curation practices for FAIR-enabling preservation and

data curation practices for digital research data objects at European level and beyond. Its primary mission is to analyse the current landscape of digital preservation and data curation practices for the long-term care of digital research objects and to create a comprehensive framework that will help digital research data repositories and archives to identify what data are candidates for digital preservation. Additionally, EOSC EDEN will develop a model for re-evaluating data throughout its lifecycle, ensuring that preservation efforts remain relevant over time. EOSC EDEN will establish an expert curation network and boost effective data preservation and curation in Europe. This paper gives a short introduction into the background and motivation, objectives, methods and expected outcomes of the EOSC EDEN project.

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I. INTRODUCTION AND PROJECT MOTIVATION

Digital preservation is an expensive process. The costs and physical limitations associated with digital storage but also with service capacity in form of human resources as well as processing cost raise the challenges of what merits digital preservation. Such challenges lead to priorities in the evaluation of data and digital objects that have lasting value for science and society and that need to be preserved for the long term.

Of course, the question “what needs to be preserved” itself is not new and (analogue) data holding institutes such as libraries and archives have been facing this dilemma for centuries. The first data archives were established in the second half of the last century, notable first examples include the Central Archive for Empirical Social Research in Cologne, Germany (now GESIS) in 1960 and UK Data Archive at the University of Essex in 1967 [1]. Development of guidelines and frameworks for data archives started in the first decade of the 21st century, with the Data Seal of Approval (2008 - 2018) and the World Data System Regular Member Certification (2011 - 2018), which both resulted in the CoreTrustSeal (since 2018) as a requirement catalogue and certification tools for Trustworthy Digital Repositories (TDR) holding data for long-term preservation [2].

Although guidelines and frameworks such as CoreTrustSeal, OAIS (ISO 14721) or PREMIS, as well as many different digital preservation tools for processes such as file format identification, characterization, migration, and emulation, they remain unevenly distributed in data repositories and archives across Europe. Furthermore, frameworks and guidelines specifically targeting the (re-)appraisal process within the digital preservation of research data are currently missing.

Aiming to tackle these challenges, the EOSC EDEN project (Grant Agreement number 10118801) [3] is a three-year (2025-2027) EU Horizon funded project involving 16 organizational partners across Europe. In this paper, we will briefly introduce the goals, methodologies, and primary expected results of EOSC EDEN to the digital preservation community. EOSC EDEN works in close collaboration with its

sister project, FIDELIS [4], that will establish a European network of FAIR-enabling trustworthy digital repositories, including training and support programmes. Both projects will complement each other to advance shared objectives related to digital preservation. As part of this partnership, a joint website (<https://eden-fidelis.eu/>) has been launched and is now accessible to the community.

II. PROJECT OBJECTIVES

To address the above challenges, especially the uneven distribution of awareness and implementation of preservation practices and standards, the EOSC EDEN project will:

- Establish a general framework and practices to support the creation of curation, digital preservation, and access strategies in Europe.
- Enrich the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) [5] with tools to store and access digital data for a long period and automate and federate certain specialized curation and preservation tasks.
- Increase adoption of curation, digital preservation, and access practices within different scientific disciplines as well as in cross-domain and digital object-based settings.
- Boost data curation and quality in Europe.
- Identify and consolidate a network of repositories and archives for digital preservation within EOSC in collaboration with the FIDELIS project.
- Contribute to the EOSC Partnership [6].

III. METHODS

Five work packages (WPs) have been set up. WP1 (“Data and Process Framework for Long-Term Digital Preservation”) will conduct a landscape analysis employing desk research and survey methods to evaluate existing frameworks, guidelines, and practices for the identification, selection, and appraisal of data for digital preservation. Information object re-use fitness will be defined using FAIR principles and digital preservation metrics. Discipline-specific requirements and needs will be defined in WP3 (“Discipline-specific Requirements, Validation and Future Use”) through desk-based mapping, survey questions and structured interviews. The EU Survey [7] platform will

be used for online surveys. The requirements derived from landscape analysis will be transformed into systems specifications by WP2 (“Long-term Access and Preservation Services & Tools”) for developing a registry and services to automate curation and preservation actions. This also provides compliance testing of services. The developed service will be implemented and assessed through use cases. All use cases implement a selection of the agreed APIs, service levels, and support arrangements to form part of an ecosystem and to integrate with the EOSC Federation. Discipline-oriented analysis and integration (WP3) will be conducted through a series of interactive pilot tests. The outcomes of EOSC EDEN will be disseminated to a broad community and experts (WP4 “Expert & Community Engagement”), ensuring its sustainability and strategic alignment with EOSC in close collaboration with FIDELIS (WP5 “Coordination, Sustainability and Strategic Alignment”).

IV. EXPECTED PROJECT OUTCOMES

Framework for identifying data for digital preservation - A framework will be developed to identify what data are candidates for digital preservation (see Figure 1). For this, three different areas of quality will be used to evaluate the digital object: the contextual data quality, including classical selection criteria such as relevance, uniqueness and reproducibility; the technical data quality, including factors such as file format sustainability, file format validation and significant properties; and the metadata quality taking into consideration aspects such as descriptive, technical and administrative metadata. In preservation processes, the quality areas need to be matched with and adapted to the designated communities’ expectations as well as to preservation objectives. At the same time, digital archives preserving the objects need to adequately support the different quality factors such as specific file formats or extraction of technical metadata. The description of the three different quality areas against archive capabilities and preservation objectives / designated community needs shall allow digital curators to better evaluate if a digital object should be preserved, what should happen to it over the course of its lifecycle and if the digital archive can meet these needs.

Figure 1. EOSC EDEN Re-Use Fitness Framework

Re-Appraisal Model - Over time, quality attributes, designated community expectations and an archive’s capabilities change. While digital preservation processes such as technology/community/preservation watch monitor these changes and may result in preservation planning and preservation action, this typically does not include a full re-appraisal process with deletion from the archive as a possible outcome. Metrics defined in the Framework (see Figure 1) will be tested against moving targets and additional metrics such as usage and impact, will be defined to describe technological fitness, completeness, and semantic quality to form a basis for re-appraisal.

User-centric operational services - Three groups of user-centric operational services will be developed: 1) a registry to expose digital preservation services to the EOSC Federation and to guide users to select the ones that fit their needs; 2) services to automate selected preservation and curation actions; and 3) standards and protocols to submit and exchange candidate packages for digital preservation (compliance).

Disciplinary support kit - Designated community needs but also contextual, technical and metadata quality criteria may be highly specific to a discipline. Due to this, generic frameworks, guidelines, and tools developed in the project need to be tested against different disciplines’ needs, resulting in target group focused training materials. A support kit targeted at different disciplines and data type-oriented communities will be developed. This support kit will build on the framework as well as on the operational services.

Expert curation network - An expert curation network will be established with representations from organizations, repositories/archives (generalist/ specialist), collections/catalogues and at the digital object type level.

In addition to achieving its primary goals, EOSC EDEN will host workshops and bootcamps to facilitate intensive discussions with curation and preservation specialists and promote peer-to-peer knowledge exchange on digital long-term preservation.

V. CONCLUSION

In summary, the EOSC EDEN project will advance digital preservation and strengthen liaison with EOSC through a series of actions and outcomes, including the development of a framework for identifying data for digital preservation, a re-appraisal model, user-centric operational services, a disciplinary support kit, and an expert curation network. Although the project is still in its early stages, it is crucial to gather feedback from international research data management, data curation and digital preservation communities on the various stages of development. By equally engaging with digital preservation specialists from the cultural heritage and the research data sectors, we hope to grow the two communities closer together, resulting in frameworks and tools that can benefit all.

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